

Research Article

Sustainable development in Physical Education and Sports: A critical appraisal of the Nigerian context

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Abstract

Physical education and sports have been used over the years by governments of developed and developing nations, through their various sports governing bodies and authorities to settle warring nations, bridge religious and ethnic crises thereby promoting national unity and economic development of such nations. Integrating physical education and sports into national development strategies, can promote health, inclusivity, community engagement and economic growth. The paper explores the potential benefits of integrating sustainable development principles in physical education and sports. The positive impacts of physical education and sports on individual health, well-being, and national development were discussed. More so, the various prospects of participating in physical activity and sports as well as the challenges hindering their sustainable development in Nigeria were also discussed. The paper advocates for the comprehensive approaches to sustainable development in physical education and sports, acknowledging the need for long term strategies that prioritize environmental conservation, social equity, and economic viability of a nation. In conclusion, the need for proper investment in physical education and sports can promote a healthier population, improve social cohesion, and boost the economics of the nation leading to sustainable development. Among others, it was recommended that provision of continuous education and training for teachers and coaches as well as investments in infrastructure, will help to encourage participation in sports, and talents discovery. This will subsequently lead to sustainable development of the nation.

Keywords: Sustainable development, physical education, sports, prospects, challenges

1. Introduction

Physical education and sports possess a profound capacity to captivate the human hearts, dismantle ethnic and religious barriers and instill skills and knowledge that extends beyond the confines of the playing fields, courts, and lawns. Sports in particular represent a universal language that transcends cultural, linguistic and socio-economic boundaries (Omobolanle, 2024). On the context of achieving sustainable development, physical education and sports focuses on creating long-term positive and considerable impacts on environmental, economic and social aspect of development in the country. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is a period of transition to the adopted 2030 agenda for sustainable development. According to Wilfred (2016), the 2030 agenda a unique opportunity to inspire global action for development worldwide, including the field of sports and physical education for development and peace. Sports and the participation in physical education activities have proven to be a cost effective and flexible tool for promoting peace and development objectives (The Common Wealth, 2021).

The United Nations Office on Sports for Development and Peace (UNOSDP) over the years, has brought people,

nations and warring communities together through sports initiatives promoting economic growth and development of such nations. Regular participation in sports and physical activities provide various social, economic, and health benefits. A number of studies conducted by the World Health Organization (WHO) highlighted that physical exercise and sports participation stimulate positive mental, health and cognitive development, which in turn is responsible for geometric economic and sustainable development of the nations (Vincent, 2023). Among the studies by WHO are, the impact of physical activity and chronic disease prevention, benefits of sports participation, global physical activity surveys, and the impact of sport participation on youth development (WHO, 2010).

According to the World Health Organization review evidence on physical activity's role in mental health, highlighted that sports participation enhances mood, reduces depression and anxiety, and improves overall psychological resilience. More so, participation can lead to increased self-esteem, leaderships skills, and social inclusion, especially for marginalized groups. The WHO recognizes sports as a vital

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component for physical development, mental, social skills development and reduction of sedentary behaviours among youth (WHO, 2014 & 2018).

The global nature of sports and physical education bring about geopolitical challenges, political tensions, and conflicts affecting the participation of nations and the hosting of international sporting events. A typical example is the 1996 Africa cup Nations hosted by South Africa of which Nigeria, been the defending champion boycotted due political differences by two countries. Sports and physical education therefore remain a platform for unity and diplomacy, economic development and social integration. Despite various economic, ethnic and religious challenges befalling Nigeria as a nation, Omobolanle (2024), reported that sports and physical activities unite communities, empower individuals and serves as a foundational force for fostering positive change on large economic scale. Sports play pivotal role in fostering development and peace by actively prolonging values such as tolerance and respect. The inclusive nature of sports and physical education activities bring individuals from diverse backgrounds and warring nations together to compete and collaborates. Sports and physical education contribute significantly to health and objectives by encouraging active lifestyle (Ajadi, 2023). This active lifestyle can be exhibited in the work place for sustainable output. Sustainable development in physical education and sports activities is vital for promoting health, social inclusion, environmental responsibility, and economic growth. In the Nigerian context, justifying sustainability in this sector involves addressing specific challenges and opportunities. To advance sustainable development therefore, Nigeria must integrate environmental protection, social inclusion, and economic viability into sports policies. In summary, sustainability in Nigerian physical education and sports activities foster a healthier, more inclusive, and environmentally responsible society, contributing to the nation's overall development (Okedeji, 2015).

2. Theoretical Frameworks for Sustainable Development in Physical Education and Sports

The theoretical framework in this context emphasizes the role of physical education and sports as a catalyst for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Nigeria. Two relevant theories are employed to demonstrate how sports promote health, social equity, environmental consciousness, and economic development. For instance, the Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) proposed by Albert Bandura, emphasize the importance of observational learning, modeling, and imitating the behaviours, attitudes, and emotional reactions of others. This theory highlights the role of self-efficacy in promoting behaviours conducive to sustainability (Bandura, 1986). In the context of physical education and sports, the SCT can be applied to promote sustainable development by fostering environmentally responsible behaviours, teamwork, and healthy lifestyles among students and athletes. And also, in building social values in students participating in sports. Similarly, Mckenzie and Lounsbury, (2013) also reported the application of the SCT in sustainable development in

physical education and sports to include modeling sustainable behaviours, building students confidence in their ability to engage in sustainable practices, providing positive reinforcement for sustainable actions and motivating students to learn behaviours by watching peers and mentors.

The Sports-for-Development theory propounded by Kidd (2008), posits that sports can drive social and economic development through community engagement, empowerment, and behavioural change. This approach leverages the universal appeal of sports to promote skills, values, social inclusion, gender equality, peace building, and environmental awareness. Integrating this concept into physical education and sports can foster sustainable development by promoting behaviours, knowledge, and attitudes that support social cohesion and environmental responsibility. The theory also emphasize that sports can be used to foster environmental stewardship and gender equality when integrated into the SDGs. The summary implications of these theories is that physical education and sports are veritable tool for sustainable national development of any nation in the planet earth.

3. Attributes of Physical Education and Sports

The vision to empower the Nigerian youth to become self-reliant and socially responsible citizens were made possible through sports participation. Physical education and sports have been used by so many countries as justifiable mechanism for foreign policy and as a veritable tool for peaceful co-existence, thereby promoting economic and social development of such nations. They engender development in all areas that enhance the standard of living of the people (Odegbami, 2020). Sports and physical education provides a cost-effective instrument to meet many development and peace challenges and also contribute expressly to sustainable development. The attributes of physical education and sports highlight the multifaceted benefits of the discipline (Physical Education and Sports) in promoting physical, mental, social, and emotional well-being of the individual and groups within the country. According to Aleksey (2020), physical education and sports encompasses a wide range of benefits. Among such include:

1. Physical education and sports helps to improve overall fitness levels, including cardiovascular endurance, muscular strength, flexibility, and body position. Participation in physical education and sport allows individual to develop and enhance various physical skills such as hand-eye coordination, agility, balance, and speed. This would enable the individual to be active and efficient at work
2. Many sport requires collaboration and teamwork, promoting social skills, communication and cooperation among participants. In sport, individuals learn the importance of discipline, hard work, and dedication in achieving goals and improving performance.
3. Regular physical activity has been shown to have positive effects on mental health, reducing stress, anxiety and depression. Success in sports and physical exercises can boost self-esteem and self-confidence at work leading to a positive self-image.
4. Participation in physical education activities and sports

involves opportunities to develop leadership skills, decision making abilities and the capacity to motivate and inspire others.

5. Health benefits of engaging in physical activities and sport reduces the risks of chronic diseases such as heart disease, diabetes, and obesity, thereby promoting long-term health and longevity.
6. Learning to win and lose graciously respect opponents to follow rules and increase the spirit of sportsmanship.
7. Developing a habit of regular physical activity and sports participation in youth can lead to a lifetime of good health and wellness.

4. Sports and Sustainable Development in Nigeria

In Nigeria, sustainable development requires an integrated and inter-disciplinary policy planning and management which transcend the parochial legal, political, environmental, economic and ethical boundaries. The Nigerian States recognize the power of sports and have used it to pursue its foreign policy and diplomatic agenda as well as foster national unity and socio-cultural integration. The introduction of National Sports Festival in 1973 was a means of fostering unity and cultural integration after the Nigeria civil war (Chinagorom, 2017). According to Vincent (2023), our lives in this contemporary times have been surrounded with one sporting activities or the other, and this is made possible by international revolution. In a country like Nigeria where politics of ethnicity has been a norm, it has now become a common sight to see people of different tribes and religion watch sports together without having recourse to tribal sentiments. Similarly, Nwankwo et al (2016), also observed that sports in Nigeria has grown from a humble beginning as an instrument of entertainment and recreational activity to a prominent phenomenon and a lucrative goldmine, breaking cultural differences among tribes and religion. The significant role of sports towards ensuring sustainable development may be summarized into the following:

1. **Social Development:** Sports has the power to bring people together, promote social cohesion, and break down barriers. By participating in sports, individuals can learn salient values such as teamwork, discipline, and respect for others, which can contribute to social harmony and development.
2. **Health and Well-being:** Engaging in sports and physical education activities can improve the overall health and well-being of the individual. By promoting a culture of physical activity through sports, Nigeria can combat lifestyle diseases, reduce healthcare costs, and improve the quality of life for its population.
3. **Economic Development:** Sport industry can be a driver of economic growth in Nigeria. By investing in sports infrastructure, promoting sport tourism, and supporting local athletes and teams, the country can create employment opportunities, generates revenue, and boost economic development.

4. **Environmental Sustainability:** By raising awareness about environmental issues, promoting co-friendly practices, sporting activities can promote and sustain the environment and this in turn may contribute more sustainable future.

4.1 Benefits of integrating sustainable development principles into Physical Education and Sports

Integrating sustainable development principles into physical education and sports offers a range of benefits. According to Ajadi (2023), some of the immediate benefits include:

1. **Environmental Awareness:** This is achieved by incorporating sustainable practices such as recycling, reducing waste, and conserving energy. Individuals and groups can develop a greater understanding of their impact on the environment.
2. **Health and Well-being:** Sustainable practices in physical education and sports can lead to a healthier environment, which in turn can have positive effects on individual health and well-being. For instance, access to clean water and air in sport facilities can contribute to a better overall individual experience.
3. **Social Responsibility:** Teaching and groups about sustainable development principles, foster a sense of social responsibility. By understanding the importance of preserving resources and minimizing waste, the individual and groups can contribute to a more sustainable future.
4. **Long time planning:** Integrating sustainable development into physical education and sports encourage the people to think long term about their actions and the impact they have on the environment. This can help to develop skills in planning and decisions making that are beneficial to both on and off the fields of play.
5. **Community Engagement:** Sustainable physical education and sports programmers often involve the community in various initiatives such as parking and clean -ups, tree planting, and fund raising for environmental causes. This will help to foster a sense of community involvement and collaboration among the general population.

4.2.Sports and Economic Development

Participation in physical activities and sports have gone beyond the level of recreational and entertainment by the participants and fans. Physical activities and sports these days have the capacity to contribute significantly to the economic development of a nation (Vincent, 2023). Sports created lots of employment to youths and young adults. Through this, additional sources of income are made through manufacturing of sports goods and products such as sports wears, balls, and other merchandise for the sports industry. The production of sports materials and equipment generate millions of naira annually for companies in particular, and

the nations in general (Head, 2006). According to Head (2006), sports equipment manufacturing gulped billions of Dollars for companies' in developed countries worldwide.

Physical education activities and sports in Nigeria have created direct and indirect employment for many youths both in formal and informal sectors of the economy (Vincent, 2023). Such job opportunities inform of viewing centres, where people watch live matches and selling of franchise of local and foreign league football idol. Betting business is another integral part of sports in recent times that have come to stay. The viewing and betting centers, generate income inform of taxes to local, state and the federal government of Nigeria. Physical education and sports can be used as a means for attaining economic and infrastructural development for global and national cohesion to the country.

A 2015 study conducted by Wilfred Eze state that physical education and sporting activities collectively benefit Nigerians and the nation at large, as it facilitates physical growth and development, mental development, emotional development and social development. Getting children and adults participate in sporting activities allows them to develop essential life skills. Moreso, the Centre for the Study of the Economics of Africa (CSEA) report that as at 2021, the impact of sports in Nigeria on the Nigerian economy is vast. A quick analysis shows that physical education and sport contributes to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), aiding employment opportunities, and has a direct multiplier effect that pertains to improvement on public health and reduction in crime waves and rates. The CSEA (2021), also reported that sports contributed 0.19%, 0.31% and 0.33% to the Nigerian GDP in 2021, 2020, and 2021 respectively, and this trends shows no sign of slowing down as the sports market in Nigeria is increasing. Similarly, the data from world bank in 2019 shows that the Nigerian economy is gaining and stabilizing steadily in GDP with a recorded growth rate 2.9% in 2023, and with a projected growth rate of 4.1% in 2026 (The Borgen Project, 2023).

4.3.Challenges Hindering Sustainable Development of Physical Education and Sports

The global nature of sporting activities brings about geopolitical challenges. Despite various economic challenges facing the country, the vast positive power and passion of sports will continue to bring people together, promoting a more inclusive, and peaceful economic ties and universal values and principles.

In Nigeria today, the increasing rate of poverty, unemployment, corruption and so many other social vices are worrisome to government and citizens of the country. Okpaku (2009) reported that due to the myriads of problem affecting the country negatively, a lot of challenges spread across various sector of the economic including sports and physical education. According to Okpaku, fraud, bribery, forgery, embezzlement, extortion, which is a product of corruption, all are bedrock of eminent challenges affecting Nigeria in general and sports in particular. In a related

scenario, Ananomo (2019) reported that inadequate physical education lectures, inadequate support by government, materials and equipment, and poor societal attitude towards physical education and sports hinder physical education and sports development for sustainable development in Nigeria. Moreso, Uduak (2007), also reported that inadequate facilities and equipment constitute some of the challenges hindering the development of physical education and sports in tertiary institutions.

The submission of Chinagorom (2017) highlighted the key challenges hindering sustainable development in physical education and sports in Nigeria to include lack of adequate funding and investments. This according to him leads to lack of proper facilities, equipment, and training for coaches and athletes. Additionally, there are also issues of outdated curriculum and teaching methods that do not align with current best practices in sports education. More so, the challenge of lack of strong grassroots development programmes to identify and nurture young talents. Without proper talents hunt, identification, and development, pathways for many potential athletes may not have the opportunity to excel in their chosen sports.

Furthermore, issues such as poor infrastructure, bureaucratic red tape, and insufficient support from government agencies can also impede the progress of physical education and sports in Nigeria. Addressing these challenges needs coordinated efforts from government, sport organizations, educational institutions, and the community to prioritize and invest in the development of physical education and sports across the country.

4.4.Prospects of Physical Education and Sports for Sustainable Development

Physical education and sports play a crucial role in contributing to sustainable development in various ways. According to Omobolane (2024), by participating in sports, young individuals will enhance their physical well-being, acquires essential knowledge and skills that can positively impact their academic performance and overall personal growth. Sports contribute significantly to health objectives by encouraging an active lifestyle. In the realm of education, sports and physical education provide valuable opportunities for learning beyond the classroom. Individuals through sports develop qualities such as time management, goal setting, and resilience, which are transferable knowledge and skills crucial for academic success (Okedeji, 2015).

Similarly, through sports, communities build connections, share experiences, and develop a sense of belonging, this help to foster a society where diversity is celebrated. According to Abass and Angba (2020), the importance of physical education and sports in achieving the SDGs, cannot be overemphasized as it is highly effective and strongly connected in actualizing the seven goals, regardless of age, color, and race. The United Nations (UN) Chronicle (2015), summarized the prospects of physical education and sports for sustainable development as follows:

1. **Health and Well-being:** Frequent and often engagement and participation in physical activities and sports are essential for promoting a healthy lifestyle, preventing diseases, and improving overall wellness of the individual. Similarly, regular physical activity reduces the risks of non-communicable diseases such as obesity, diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases or disorders.
2. **Environmental Sustainability:** Sports and participation in physical activities raises awareness about environmental issues or challenges and promote eco-friendly practices. For instance, promoting sports and physical activities that rely on natural resources and encouraging environmentally friendly events can contribute to a more sustainable future.
3. **Social Inclusion:** Physical education and sport have the power and tenacity to bring people from diverse backgrounds together, fostering social inclusion and cohesion. By encouraging teamwork, fair play, and mutual respect, physical education and sport can help to build more inclusive communities.
4. **Economic Development:** Sports industry can drive economic development through job creation, tourism, and infrastructure development. Investing in sport facilities, training programmes, and events can stimulate local economies and create opportunities for growth
5. **Education and Skills Development:** Physical education and sport teaches important life skills such as discipline, perseverance, and teamwork. By incorporating sports into educational curricular students can develop both physical and cognitive abilities, preparing them for future challenges.

4.5. Positive impacts of Physical Education and Sports on Health, Well-being and National Development

Physical education and sports plays a vital role in the Nigerian educational system leading to healthy and active life, from being physically fit, to team work and then to the improvement of fine and gross motor skills (Canadian Educational Centre, 2023).

The Educational Centre also added that participation in physical education and sport also ensure that physical and mental well-being of the individual is promoted thereby fostering the attainment of social Skills that expressly contribute to national development and economic growth. Specifically, National Library of Medicine (2013), reported that physical activity reduces the risk for heart disease, diabetes mellitus, osteoporosis, high blood pressure; it improves various aspects of health and fitness, including aerobic capacity, muscle and bone strength, flexibility, insulin sensitivity, and lipid profiles. Being physically active can improve one's brain health, helps in managing weight gain, reduce the risk of diseases, strengthen bones and muscles, and improve one's ability to participate in daily or everyday activities (CDC, 2023). Similarly, Golan (2022) categorized the positive impacts of physical education and sport on health and national development as follows:

1. **Health Impacts:** Regular participation in sporting activities helps to improve overall health by promoting physical fitness, reducing the risk of chronic diseases such as obesity, diabetes, and heart disease, and at the same time improve cardiovascular and respiratory on mental health.
2. **Mental Well-being impacts:** Physical activity has been shown to have positive effects on mental by reducing stress, anxiety, and depression. Sports can also help to improve mood, self-esteem, and cognitive function.
3. **Social Benefits/Impacts:** Engaging in sports and physical activities helps individuals develop social skills such as teamwork, leaderships, communication, and cooperation. This can help to foster a sense of community belonging.
4. **Economic Impacts:** The sporty industry can have a significant economic impact by creating jobs, boosting tourism through sporting events and generating revenue through sports-related products and services.
5. **On the side of national development,** investing in physical education and sporting activities can contribute to national development by promoting a healthier population, reducing healthcare costs, and improve productivity. Sports can also help to promote national unity, identity and pride

4.6. Approaches towards Sustainable Development of Physical Education and Sports

Sustainable development in physical education and sports encompasses a variety of strategies aimed at fostering long-term well-being, for individuals and communities. According to Wilfred (2016), the approaches are geared towards repositioning physical education and sports for sustainable development. Some of these approaches include:

1. **Inclusive Programming and Design:** Physical education and sports programme should have a diverse range of capacity backgrounds and interests. The programme and design should ensure that every individuals and groups are engaged. Individuals should be encouraged to participate in sports and physical education, and it should be voluntary.
2. **Promotion of Health and Wellness:** Physical education and sports programme should emphasize the importance of healthy lifestyle choices, physical fitness, and mental well-being. Habits should encourage overall well-being should be encouraged
3. **Environmental Sustainability:** There is need to integrate eco-friendly practices into sports and physical education programme. Practices such as promoting non-toxic equipment, reducing waste, and using energy-efficient facilities. Individuals and groups should be educated on the importance of environmental conservation.
4. **Fostering Community Participation:** Community engagement through partnerships with local communities, organizations and business to support physical education initiatives, and encourage collaboration and participation from a wide range of stakeholders.
5. **Lifelong Learning:** Physical education and sports should be geared towards promoting continuous learning and

skills development. Such skills would enable the individual to pursue personal growth and development in their various places of work. All these comprehensive approaches are top notch for sustainable national development.

5. Conclusion

Achieving sustainable development in physical education and sports in Nigeria is crucial for the overall well-being and growth of the nation. By proper investment in physical education and sports, Nigeria can promote a healthier population, improve social cohesion, and boost the economy through the development of sports talent. Prospects for such may include increasing awareness of the benefits of physical activity improving infrastructure for sports facilities, and implementing policies that support sports development. Moreso, challenges do exist, such as inadequate funding, lack of proper training and development opportunities for athletes and coaches, as well as mismanagement in sports governance. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach involving government support, private sector investment and collaboration with international sports organizations. Overall, sustainable development in physical education and sports in Nigeria is an attainable goal but requires commitment resources and effective strategies to overcome the obstacles currently hindering such progress.

Recommendations:

Achieving sustainable development in physical education and sports in Nigeria is a complex but vital goal. The following recommendations may be needed.

- There is need for investment in infrastructure. Such investment will help to encourage participation and talent development.
- There is need for the provision of continuous education and training of teachers and coaches. This will help to enhance skills development and promote best practices.
- Need to encourage participation in variety of sports at all levels to promote physical activity and talent identification,
- There is also need for public-private-partnerships (PPP). Such partnerships will help in the area of sports facilities and equipment provision.
- Need for public support. This will develop and enforce physical education and sports participation in schools and communities.
- There is need to support research initiatives in identifying trends, challenges and opportunities in sports development.

Abbreviations

UNOSDP: United Nations Office on Sports for Development and Peace
Ultraviolet

SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals

WHO: World Health Organization

SCT: Social Cognitive Theory

CSEA: Centre for the Study of the Economics of Africa

GDP: Gross Domestic Product

UN: United Nations

PPP: Public Private Partnership

CDC: Centre for Disease Control

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Conflicts of Interest

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